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A CASE OF THE APPLICATION OF CUSTOMIZED STANDARDIZATION ON FLORAL DESIGN AT CN FLOWER

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ABSTRACT

Recently, floral design and decorations have been closely related in our lives. However, how a floral design firm adopts an appropriate strategy to strengthen its competitive advantage in a highly competitive market environment is an issue that needs urgent exploration. This paper aims to conduct a case study on a successful floral design firm, CN Flower (hereafter CN), which has the highest sales volume in Taiwan. Why and how the CN floral design could be successfully achieved is the focus of this study. By adopting customized standardization as a service mode, the study found that CN can not only satisfy the needs of the customer, but also offer direct benefits for the company. Thus, the results of this study may help to uncover the possible benefits of adopting the customized standardization as a feasible service design strategy.

Keywords: Floral Design, Customized Standardization, Case Study

INTRODUCTION

Good floral decorations and displays can enhance the quality of life. In the last thirty years, the planted area used for the flower market in Taiwan has increased over 10 times, while the sales value of the flower market has increased 223 times (planted area in 1971 = 1,242 hectares with a sales value of 53 million NTD; the current planted area = 13,109 hectares with a sales value of 11,830 million NTD). As we know, the prosperity of the flower market has also increased market demands for floral design and services. However, no empirical evidence is yet available to confirm what service design strategies

should be adopted for floral design firms which could augment their competitiveness.

Founded in 1988, CN plays a leading role in the floral design in Taiwan. Floral design is the core business in CN. Floral services in CN include wedding decorations, fashion shows, packing designs for banquets and flowerpots, the provision of floral materials for restaurants, hotels, and department stores, and various other types of floral services. Compared to other floral design firms, CN offers a wider variety of floral services for the customer. In addition, CN treats flowers as the visual focus and believes that excessive decoration can overshadow the nature of beauty. Thus, CN's focus on stylish floral design does successfully attract the customer. Currently, CN has become a floral design firm with the highest sales volume in Taiwan, and her success is undoubtedly worth probing.

Lampel and Mintzberg (1996) proposed a continuum of strategies (Figure 1) to categorize services into three major types: pure standardization, customized standardization and pure customization. In Taiwan, most services rendered by floral design firms can be categorized as either pure standardization or pure customization. By contrast, CN exclusively focuses on customized standardization. Thanks to the coexistence of the "rapid production" and "tailored" to customer needs in the Taiwan flower market, floral services have been mainly led to the way of pure standardization or pure customization. In this study, we will explore the characteristics of these three service modes, and discover how CN operates successfully as a floral design firm.

Figure 1 A continuum of strategies (Lampel and Mintzberg, 1996, p. 24)

LITERATURE

FLORAL SERVICE MODES IN TAIWAN

Taiwan's main floral services are pure standardization or pure customization. Firstly, pure standardization is a production-oriented service. In this service mode, it is assumed that the customers are a homogenous group, and thus meets the criteria for mass production (Kurokawa, 2003). It is a large and "fast production" process where products will not be altered based on the needs of a variety of customers. True to the characteristics of pure standardization, standardized parts (floral materials) and uniform operating procedures are used to reduce human errors and bias. At the same time, minimal time and costs may be applied. Improvement in production reliability can be achieved so that customers will not experience a sense of disappointment or failure, thus increasing customer satisfaction (Wang, Wang, Ma, and Qiu, 2010). This is done in order to achieve cost minimization, whilst maximizing efficiency at the same time. From the viewpoint of a service provider, the pure standardization service mode is used by a floral service firm to produce bouquets in accordance with standardized blueprints. This can save time and on-site production costs for customers. It can also reduce production time and increase efficiency. When a customer buys a standardized bouquet, he/she can save waiting time. It is also easy to meet customer satisfaction since the standardization of commodities is not comparative. In view of this, the

use of a pure standardization service mode can be chosen for both firm profits and customer satisfactions, with the added benefits of no customization in terms of features and performance practices.

However, Moritz (2005) pointed out that customers cannot be standardized, since they have individual needs and expectations. In particular, when there is a market demand for heterogeneity or there are other competitors (Peters and Saidin, 2000), customization can create and deliver superior customer values (Treacy and Wiersema, 1993). Therefore, when retailers customize according to customer needs and provide appropriate products, customers will be willing to spend more money to buy the customized solutions (Wang et al., 2010). A feature of pure customization is that production only starts after an order is taken. The customer's needs and wants can be completely met (tailor-made) with regards to design, manufacture, installation, and distribution. From the service provider's viewpoints, a pure customization service mode, making products in accordance with customers' preferences and demand, might ensure that the ideals of customers and customers' satisfaction can be achieved. This can in turn increase the possibility that customers will continue buying goods. Although the waiting time and costs of flowers will increase relatively for the customer, product quality can be ensured in the process of providing this type of service. Nevertheless, customization means a need for higher costs. What would happen if there were conflicts

encountered? Poor communication may easily lead to higher fees being paid by the customer or the customer not being satisfied with the product. This service mode is thus not necessarily accompanied with service satisfaction (Bardakci and Whitelock, 2004).

Therefore, the use of pure standardization can not only reduce costs, reduce risk, and improve operational efficiency, but also lower costs connected to customer feedback. Then, it could be also true that pure customization may result in lower efficiency and higher costs, but it can satisfy customer needs more effectively and improve customer satisfaction (Wang et al., 2010). However, in a competitive floral services market, neither the service mode of pure customization nor that of pure standardization can be used alone to meet market demand. Consequently many firms may understand that customization is very important, but they still continue to strengthen the standardization aspects of their business (Sandoff, 2005). This is a strategy that can reduce costs, improve efficiency, and ensure customer satisfaction (Wang et al., 2010). The following paragraphs will discuss CN's service mode of customized standardization and explore what features it has. In addition, we will compare the customized standardization mode to the conventional floral service modes used in Taiwan, to see how it differs from pure standardization and pure customization.

CUSTOMIZED STANDARDIZATION

As mentioned above, a standardized service mode can provide reliability and reduction of errors, while customization can improve in meeting customers' unique needs (Wang et al., 2010). In providing services, both service quality and efficiency must be taken into consideration. If lower costs, reliability, and high productivity are to be achieved and maintained, whilst satisfying customers' needs or other purposes, we need to have comprehensive standardization and customization in the product service process (Wang et al., 2010). Currently, CN is the only company in the Taiwan floral market that has adopted customized standardization to provide floral services and designs. Customized standardization is a new method to present parts (floral materials) in a modular way to achieve

customized products and services. It allows the customer to combine in a slightly limited way; their own needs and preferences (customized) with modular parts (standardized) before the product go into assembly. Therefore, this service mode is a way of integrating pure standardization and pure customization to meet customers' specific needs. Customized standardization is not only a client-oriented service mode, but also provides a stable operation for better services (McCutcheon, Raturi, and Meredith, 1994). Furthermore, Jussi Heikkilä (2002) proposed that the customized standardization service mode is often preferred as part of strategy development, as it can shorten the time and cost required for design and production. In view of this, service firms should apply advanced technology to explore various possible ways to balance standardization and customization (Cao, Wang, Law, Zhang, and Li, 2006). Currently, the advantages of the customized standardization service mode have been realized. However, how does CN successfully apply this mode? The solution to the question is what this study focuses on.

CASE STUDY

METHODOLOGY

Halinen and Törnroos (2005) highlighted that case studies are especially suitable for analyzing business models and business performance in specific contexts. This study adopted semi-structured interviewing methods to obtain valuable insights about CN's business operations from two CN service superintendents. In this study, two research assistants participated in the interview: one typed the interview responses word for word and the other recorded and raised interview questions. All interviews were tape-recorded and photographed. In this study, we further conducted 4 in-depth interviews with CN's CEO (chief executive officer). Each in-depth interview lasted between 2 and 3 hours on average. The interview is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2 Two CN service superintendents and interviews

BACKGROUND

The object of this case study is CN as a floral design firm in Taiwan. The firm was founded by Alfie Lin, a creative director, in 1988 (Figure 3). At that time, the Taiwan flower market was popular with multi-level packaging and packaging bouquets with a combination of accessories. However, Alfie considered that such excessive packaging could damage the natural beauty of flowers. Therefore, CN adopted simple packaging materials to allow flowers to be the visual focus (Figure 4). CN's natural and simplistic style of a product presentation represents a simple image of an elegant bouquet. This unique design style was, and still is, loved by the local people. Consequently, CN floral design can be seen at many major events/ activities and in magazines, which have gradually laid a foundation for CN leading in the floral design sector. In addition, unlike traditional floral design firms with the floral design as their business item, CN's total service items include: wedding flower arrangements, floral designs for fashion shows, bouquets or potted plants, and provision of services, flower materials and/or floral designs for restaurants, hotels, and department stores. Therefore, in addition to market demand for integrating floral designs, CN provides more services to more customers. CN would like to provide a total new holistic service experience to the customer. Financially, CN has gradually achieved a 10% monthly growth rate through the use of unique floral designs and diverse floral service items. From a position of being "in the red" at its start, CN currently averages an annual sales turnover of approximately NT\$25 million, making it the floral design firm with the highest sales turnover in Taiwan.

Figure 3 CN Flower brand image

Figure 4 CN Flower Flower-design products

FINDINGS

SERVICE OVERVIEW OF CN

This overview identifies the issues in floral service delivery that CN encountered in the past and explains how CN shifted to adopt customized standardization. In fact, there was no clear definition of a service mode for CN when it started doing business. CN's current system was established based on the experiences of past struggles and failures. Initially, CN provided a pure customized service, and customers ordered the goods directly from the floral designer (Figure 5). As pure customization is about tailor-made products, the customers would explain to the designer when ordering what kind of bouquet in what style they want. The designer would then proceed to design products according to this communication. Later, however, CN found that in such a mode, it would be easy for customers and designers to have cognitive differences and misunderstandings, resulting in customer complaints or return of the goods. One CN superintendent pointed out:

*"Style is a very subjective thing. For example, a customer wants to buy a **noble** bouquet. While in the designer's own opinion, he/she made a **noble** bouquet of flowers, the customer may not think so."*

As a result of repeated customer complaints and goods returned, CN employed a project manager to coordinate communications between customers and designers (Figure 6). In this new purchasing order procedure, customers needed to order products (or design) from the project manager. The project manager was also responsible for the discussion concerning the desired style of a product. After a complete understanding of the customer's idea, the designer would then make the product according to the customer's needs. When the product is completed, the project manager will check whether the product is consistent with the idea of the customer to ensure that the product meets the customer's demand. After this purchasing order procedure was implemented, the CN CEO said: *"The project manager has enhanced communication with customers, so customers' complaints were significantly reduced, while customer satisfaction has been improved."* Although customers' complaints were reduced after the implementation of the new product ordering

procedure, CN still found that customers and designers had cognitive differences, which occurred regularly. Although CN's pure customization services mode was tailored for customers, it increased the burden on the designers. To solve this problem, CN began to try a pure standardization mode to serve customers via an online store where customers could see the actual products, to ensure customers that bought products of their own liking. However, the CN CEO stressed that:

"Customers often have different liking for bouquets based on age, gender, preferences, etc. So, pure standardization does not satisfy all customers. As a result, pure standardization cannot satisfy all customers."

Thus, in order to meet customer needs and economic benefits, CN has gradually applied the customized standardization mode to provide floral services. In using the customized standardization mode, customers can now confirm the style and pattern of a product on the web site. If customers then have special preferences, some floral materials can be replaced to meet customer demand and improve customer satisfaction. In addition, the CN CEO also found that this service did help the project manager in more effective communication with customers. It also meant that the designers did not have to spend a lot of time in style innovation, enabling them to focus more on the flower products and also maintain a good quality of product. Therefore, compared to competitors who provide either pure standardization or pure customization services, customized standardization can save redesign time as well as maintain the existing quality level of products. Furthermore, it also meets the needs of customers. Through the customized standardization mode, CN plans to ensure the continued provision of floral products that is consistent with customers' needs and standards, even under circumstances of limited resources.

Figure 5 Product purchasing order before modification

Figure 6 Product purchasing order after modification

CN'S FLORAL SERVICE DESIGN MODE

CN's operational mode of the customized standardization is derived from long-term experiences. This study will explore how CN successfully operates the customized standardization service mode in floral design. First, CN's simple but elegant floral designs and styles have become a major image. However, to cope with fashion and trend changes, CN will set a different theme of style every year. The design director and designers will design several styles of products in accordance with the theme of the year, and then place the styles on the website directory. CN has two physical channels, i.e. stores and department stores, while also providing a network platform for purchases directly, or ordering through telephones or faxes, as shown in Figure 7. First, the customer can refer to the current bouquet style as displayed on the website directory. If the customer sees a specific product they like as it is displayed on the website, they can order it directly. However, if the customer has a need based on special preferences or conditions, CN will ask the customer to choose a matching style from the website directory. They will then communicate with the customer to replace limited floral materials, change colors and/or do minor style modifications in customizing the product for the customer. It is vital at this stage that both sides establish a good foundation of communication. This is one of the most crucial aspects of the customized standardization service mode. In addition, it is worth mentioning that CN intends to maintain its unique brand image. To ensure this, they have developed their own product packaging, and have applied for patents. It can be seen that in addition to having a good brand image and unique floral styles, CN applies customized standardization of the floral service mode to meet the specific needs of the customer. This is one of the main reasons why CN is so loved by the public. The CN success story can be found in a major marketing advantage that customized floral products can be made, incorporating a standardized modular production mode. In general, the following aspects illustrated the effects of CN's customized standardization service. First, as for customers, the customized standardization service mode allows the customers to choose standardized products based on product

categories. If the customers prefer customized products over standardized ones, they can choose one standardized design and ask CN to alter certain product components, such as the flower colors or flower types, according to their own preferences. CN's superintendents stress that, since customers' perceptions of beauty vary, a customized standardization service prevents customers from choosing unwanted and unexpected products, while increasing customer satisfaction simultaneously. Secondly, as for the firm, CN provides examples of standardized products and modifies certain parts of the products to make them more customized. Therefore, different floral designers can produce consistent styles without wasting time on innovating new styles. They can be more attentive to floral products to ensure service quality, and effectively minimize the costs and time needed for product manufacturing. As a result, the customized standardization service has the advantages of standardization and customization, and can make a balance between business efficiency and customer needs.

Figure 7 Product ordering procedure

CONCLUSION

In this study, CN's development, implementation and successful operation of the customized standardization service mode is explored and compared to other floral service modes in Taiwan. The findings of the study have shown that the customized standardization service mode employed by CN, has great potential for success in the floral design market in Taiwan. It draws on the benefits and advantages of existing modes while limiting their disadvantages and shortcomings. From the perspective of service design provision, if customer's demand quality and business efficiency at the same time (increasing predictability, production rate and customer satisfaction), it is necessary for firms to develop procedures that integrate standardization and customization (Wang, Wang, Ma, & Qiu, 2010).

Hence, this case suggested that in order to generate stable economic output and satisfy customer demands, CN's customized standardization service mode, namely dissecting service into components and reassembling them, could indeed curtail the time and costs spent on production and design in a competitive flower market. Wang et al. (2010) pointed out when service provisions and products are nearly at the same quality level, a firm should maintain the goal of standardization and customization; otherwise customer satisfaction will deteriorate. In view of this, a customized standardization is a feasible service design strategy to strike a balance between the benefits of a floral design firm and the demands of the customer. This case show the application of customized standardization strategy can bring more benefits to floral design industry.

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